

MUSIC RECOMMENDATION SYSTEM BASED ON EMOTION DETECTION

Mrs. Suma Rajesh A¹, Parvashree H M², Poonam³, Srishti srivastava⁴, Sushma Srikanta Kurandwad⁵ ¹Assistant Professor, ^{2,3,4,5}Under Graduate Student
Dept of Computer Science and
Engineering K S Institute of
Technology, Bengaluru

ABSTRACT: In an decreasingly digital and the data-driven world, personalization of services and happy recommendation is an important aspect to ameliorate the user experience. In recent times, there has been a vast elaboration in the music recommendation system, were the fastening on the user emotion and the song characteristics. The proposed system takes advantage of the idea that visual stimulants, similar to the content of images, can be used to detect the user's emotional state. By recycling the facial expressions and other visual cues of the user, the system detects and classifies feelings according to the emotions similar as happiness, sadness, wrathfulness and others. This emotional data is also used to detect the music that is aligned to detected emotional state of the user. The recommendation system are displayed according to the rulings that enable song recommendation on the bases of the user's preferences or the current emotions.

Keywords: - Image Processing (IP), Face Emotion Detection, Music Recommendation.

I. INTRODUCTION

The domain of music recommendation has undergone substantial development, which involves an array of algorithms and methodologies crafted to facilitate the users in discovering music that aligns with their preferences. Typically, these systems leverage implicit preferences and listening history along with user emotions to produce.

Music plays a vital role in our daily lives and has a deep effect on human emotions. Given the influence of music on our feelings and experiences, there is an increasing need for music recommendation systems that are sensitive to the emotional demands of their users. This study attempts to fill the gap by using an image processing and emotion identification system for music recommendations. It presents a novel method that considers users' emotional states in real time. The system can recommend music that not only fits the user's music tastes but also enables to express the feelings they are experiencing at the moment.

Because it focus on the emotional understanding over other factors, this signifies the way we think about recommending music. Facial expressions are captured and interpreted by the system to identify emotions like happy , sad , angry.

II. LITURATURE SURVEY

1.A survey of music emotion recognition

Music is the language of emotions. In recent years, music emotion recognition has attracted widespread attention in the academic and industrial community since it can be widely used in fields like recommendation systems, automatic music composing, psychotherapy, music visualization, and so on. Especially with the rapid development of artificial intelligence, deep learning-based music emotion recognition is gradually becoming mainstream. This paper gives a detailed survey of music emotion recognition. Starting with some preliminary knowledge of music emotion recognition, this paper first introduces some commonly used evaluation metrics. Then a three-part research framework is put forward. Based on this three-part research framework, the knowledge and algorithms involved in each part are introduced with detailed analysis, including some commonly used datasets, emotion models, feature extraction, and emotion recognition algorithms. After that, the challenging problems and development trends of music emotion recognition technology are proposed, and finally, the whole paper is summarized

2.Music Recommendation Based on Face Emotion Recognition

In there paper a new approach for playing music automatically using facial emotion. Most of the existing approaches involve playing music manually, using wearable computing devices, or classifying based on audio features. Instead, we propose to change the manual sorting and playing. We have used a Convolutional Neural Net-work for emotion detection. For music recommendations, Pygame & Tkinter are used. Our proposed system tends to reduce the computational time involved in obtaining the results and the overall cost of the designed system, thereby increasing the system's overall accuracy. Testing of the system is done on the FER2013 dataset. Facial expressions are captured using an inbuilt camera. Feature extraction is performed on input face images to detect emotions such as happy, angry, sad, surprise, and neu-tral. Automatically music playlist is generated by identifying the current emotion of the user. It yields better performance in terms of computational time, as compared to the algorithm in the existing literature.

3.Study on Music Emotion Recognition Based on the Machine Learning Model Clustering Algorithm

In the paper its given as , in the recent years, the explosive growth of online music resources makes it difficult to retrieve and manage music information. To efficiently retrieve and classify music information has become a hot research topic. ayer's two-dimensional emotion plane is selected as the basis for establishing the music emotion database. Music is divided into .ve categories, the concept of continuous emotion perception is introduced, and music emotion is regarded as a point on a two-dimensional emotional plane, together with the two sentiment variables to determine its location. e artificial labelling method is used to determine the position range of they types of emotions on the emotional plane, and the regression method is used to obtain the relationship between the VA value and the music features so that the music emotion classification problem is transformed into a regression problem. A regression based music emotion classification system is designed and implemented, which mainly includes a training part and a testing part. In the training part, three algorithms, namely, polynomial regression, support vector regression, and k-plane piecewise regression, are used to obtain the regression model. In the test part, the input music data is regressed and predicted to obtain its VA value and then classified, and the system performance is considered by classification accuracy. Results show that the combined method of support vector regression and k-plane piecewise regression improves the accuracy by 3 to 4 percentage points compared to using one algorithm alone; compared with the traditional classification method based on a support vector machine, the accuracy improves by 6 percentage points. Music emotion is classified by algorithms such as support vector machine classification, K- neighborhood classification, fuzzy neural network classification, fuzzy K-neighborhood classification, Bayesian classification, and Fisher linear discrimination, among which the support vector machine, fuzzy K-neighborhood, and the accuracy rate of music emotion classification realized by Fisher linear discriminant algorithm are more than 80%; a new algorithm "mixed classifier" is proposed, and the music emotion recognition rate based on this algorithm reaches 84.9%

III PROPOSED ALGORITHM

Local Binary Patterns Histogram(LBPH)

The LBPH algorithm, standing for Local Binary Patterns Histogram, is a technique used primarily in computer vision for tasks like texture classification and facial recognition. It works by breaking down an image into small regions, then computing a binary pattern for each pixel within these regions based on a comparison with its neighboring pixels. These binary patterns are aggregated into histograms, which essentially count the occurrences of different patterns within each region. By concatenating these histograms from all regions, LBPH creates a feature vector that captures the overall texture information of the image. This feature vector is particularly useful in tasks like facial recognition, as it remains robust against changes in lighting conditions and facial expressions. Essentially, LBPH provides a compact yet informative representation of image textures, enabling accurate classification and recognition even in challenging scenarios.

Haar Cascade

The Haar Cascade face detection algorithm utilizes a cascade of classifiers to detect objects, particularly faces, in images or video frames. It operates by scanning the image with a series of rectangular filters at different scales and locations, identifying regions that match patterns resembling facial features. By combining multiple classifiers in a cascade, the algorithm efficiently filters out non-face regions, enabling accurate and real-time face detection in various applications.

Fisher face

The Fisher face algorithm, also known as Fisher's Linear Discriminant Analysis (FLDA) for face recognition, reduces the dimensionality of face images while maximizing the ratio of between-class variance to within-class variance. It achieves this by projecting face images onto a lower-dimensional subspace where the differences between classes are maximized. This compact representation enables efficient classification of faces, making it a popular method for facial recognition tasks.

IV PROPOSED METHOD

- Data Collection were we collected a dataset of images of emotions of user and music preference conditions from a group of users. The users were asked to hear to music when detecting face emotions were accordingly using a camera. They were also asked to rate the music application they heard on their emotional response accordingly.
- Facial Expression Analysis We used a deep literacy- grounded model for facial expression analysis. The model had multiple convolutional layers, which were followed by fully linked layers that discovered the relationships between expressions and emotions on the face. The model comported of several convolutional layers followed by completely connected layers that learned mappings between facial emotions and expressions. Emotions are classified into several orders, like similar as happy, sad, angry, and neutral.
- Music recommendation We used a cooperative filtering algorithm for music recommendation. The algorithm generates the music recommendations grounded on the user's emotional state prognosticated by a facial expression analysis model.
- Evaluation estimated the performance of the proposed system by measuring its delicacy in prognosticating the stoner's emotional state and its effectiveness in furnishing substantiated music recommendations. We also conducted a study to estimate the effectiveness of the system and to improve the substantiated music recommendations.
- Results The results indicate that the proposed system can directly prognosticate the stoner's emotional state and give individualized music recommendations that match their mood. The system achieved the high delicacy in prognosticating the user's emotional state, with the attained an averageF1 score of 0.85.
- Overall, the proposed system demonstrated the effectiveness of analyzing the facial expression and cooperative filtering in a music recommendation system to give individual the recommendations of sings that match the user's emotional state. The system has the implicit to ameliorate stoner satisfaction and engagement with music recommendation systems by furnishing more accurate and individualized recommendations.

V.RESULTS

A music recommendation system utilizing emotion detection technology analyzes the user's emotional state through various cues such as facial expressions, voice tone, or biometric data. By understanding the user's mood, preferences, and context, the system generates personalized playlists or song recommendations that align with their current emotional needs. Leveraging machine learning algorithms, it continuously refines its recommendations based on user feedback, ensuring a more accurate and enjoyable music discovery experience.

VI.CONCLUSION

Imagine having a music recommendation system that's like having your own personal DJ. But instead of just guessing what songs you might enjoy, it pays attention to how you're feeling in the moment. This system uses advanced technology to analyze subtle cues like your facial expressions or even your heart rate to understand if you're happy, sad, or somewhere in between.

Once it understands your mood, it suggests songs that match how you're feeling. So, if you're feeling pumped up and energetic, it might queue up some high-tempo tracks to keep you motivated. On the other hand, if you're feeling more relaxed or contemplative, it might offer soothing melodies to help you unwind.

Think of it as having a musical mood ring that instantly selects the perfect song for any emotional state. And the more you interact with the system, the better it becomes at understanding your unique preferences and emotions, fine-tuning its recommendations over time.

So, the next time you're feeling a bit down or in need of a mood boost, all you have to do is let your music recommendation system know. In just moments, it'll curate a playlist tailored specifically to lift your spirits and enhance your mood, making your listening experience truly personalized and enjoyable.

VII REFERENCES

- [1] Olga Sourina ,Yisi Liu, Minh Khoa Nguyen “Real-Time EEG-Based Emotion Recognition For Music Therapy” Published by journal on Multimodal User Interfaces – Springer International Publishing on 2012 5:27-35.
- [2] Anna Bukowska, Krzysztof Stachyra, Amelia Oldfield “Musical Therapy and Emotional Expression: A kaleidoscope of Perspective” Edited by Ludwika Konieczna–Nowak Published by Katowise ISBN: 978-83942090-3-2 on 2016.
- [3] Ramya Ramanathan, Radha Kumaran, Ram rohan, Rajat Gupta, Vishalakshi Prabhu “An Intelligent Music Player Base On Emotion Recognition” Published By IEEE International Conference On Computational Systems And Information Technology For Sustainable Solutions 2017 Page no 299-303.
- [4] Aurobind V. Iyer, Viral Pasad, Karan Prajapati “Emotion Based Mood Enhancing Music Recommendation” Published by IEEE International conference on RTEICT, May 2017,India. Page No: 1573-1577.